

Information Literacy using Open Education Platforms & Resources: Case Study of Central Library of COEP Technological University

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Abstract:- In the current scenario the libraries crossed the all boundaries of its traditional accessing system today's Librarian are not custodian but the information officers. The College of Engineering Pune chartered in 1854 is a nationally respected leader in technical education the library has a varied collection of books, periodicals, dissertation e- books, e- databases, e- journals,. A large number of National and International Print/Online Journals are subscribed covering all disciplines. The Library of College of Engineering Pune is a technology embracing library.

Information literacy means knowing when and why you need information where to find it and how to evaluate. Open education platform and open education system gives an huge opportunities to for learners. Use of Information technology, various search engines, browsers, wikis and the widespread diffusion of information technology give rise to education system in India at the same time Libraries in India facing challenges regarding how teaching and learning should be organized & carried out. Academic Libraries in India have been using internet and other digital technology based services to users. The open education resources aim to provide all type of unreachable, unaffordable data to users without barriers and to encourage and enable to get new information freely This article will be helpful for studying the open education platforms & advantage and disadvantages, how to make them available to users and available open education platform for users in COEP Tech. University library.

Keywords:- Information Literacy, Open education platforms, COEP University.

I. INTRODUCTION

Over the last one decade digital India has transformed day to day lives of citizens this was an positive impact on lives of individual mission digital is empowered various sector of Indian society and education is one of them. During the covid pandemic each and everyone experienced importance of digital platform when school and colleges had been shut down. In the current scenario of ICT, education in most of the universities and colleges is being operated by technology and innovations. The educational Institutions have responded to those changes and embraced the digital mode of education involving both teaching and learning. Information explosion make a problem of managing information it's a big challenge for LIS professional. ICT based services made this easy to facilitate users on time also its reduces the workload of librarian various library software, open sources software's available on one finger click. It's save the time of readers as well library staff.

II. THE INFORMATION LITERACY?

“Information literacy is the set of integrated abilities encompassing the reflective discovery of information, the understanding of how information is produced and valued, and the use of information in creating new knowledge and participating ethically in communities of learning.”

Information literacy is the ability to recognize the extent and nature of an information need, then to locate, evaluate, and effectively use the needed information. (Plattsburgh State Information and Computer Literacy Task Force, 2001)

The concept of information literacy has progressed beyond how to find books in the library. Many aspects of information literacy are essential components of education.

The amount of information available in COEP Tech. University through electronic form, like e- journals /databases, e- books, e- papers and the internet is both exhilarating and overwhelming. Student of COEP have more expectation from library to get desired information quickly. Librarian plays a vital role to make the all type of information available in their stack.

Information Literacy can be defined as a process of attaining knowledge.

Fig. 1: Information literacy

Information literacy empowers in all walk of life to seek, evaluate, use create information effectively also help to achieve personal goals. People who are knowledge seeker want to enhance their skill, intellectual capacity to brighten the future or contribute in nation's development are using information sources effectively. It is narrowest sense that information literacy includes only access of digital content or to know the electronic content cloud based services and use of technology that they have but the information literacy means use of all kind of information incorporate into knowledge sometimes it is in print form, electronic form, audio-video or in rare types information material like clay, papyrus, wax and parchment, etc. Though your library does not have all type of library material which you want but your librarian can give you a path to know how to reach towards to get the desired one. Libraries have been providing various types of users education programs to facilitate use of library and information resources. Library orientation is one of the activities organized every year especially for new admitted student to know physical set up of libraries, library rules, services, facilities provided by libraries. There is need of such user education programs to use library resources efficiently & effectively. Display of new arrivals using innovative ideas to attract users, COEP Library organize various activity like Human library symposium, round table discussion on old periodicals magazines, book exhibition.etc.

III. OPEN EDUCATION PLATFORMS

The term open educational resources first came into use at a conference hosted by UNESCO in 2002, defined as "the open provision of educational resources, enabled by information and communication technologies, for consultation, use and adaptation by a community of users for noncommercial purposes" (Johnstone, 2005).

Open Educational Resources (OER) are learning, teaching and education materials in any format and medium are either in the public domain or published under open licenses are under copyright. That permits no-cost access, re-use, and re-purpose, adaptation and redistribution by others.

In other word we can say the material which is available freely in digitized form for student, educators, self learner, for non commercial purpose.OER encourages the new learner to motivate them to do different things. Openly licensed freely available material can be modified by users.

IV. OBJECTIVES OF STUDY

The main objective of this study is to find out the available OER at COEP Technological University.

- To find out the student's level of awareness of OER
- To ensure the student's level of usage of OER
- To find the usability of OER

V. HYPOTHESIS

This study is based on simple hypothesis.

There is a significant relationship between awareness and use of OER by students of COEP Tech. University. Student of COEP Tech. University aware about the OER and therefore they use the OER efficiently.

VI. LITERATURE REVIEW

To examine the usability of open education platform (OER) in COEP tech university researcher conducted a cross sectional study. Total 250 students chosen by using systematic random sampling method 100 students from B. tech, 100 students from M. tech, 50 PhD students. Users of COEP Tech University use Open education platforms for their information need also the online questionnaire

circulated within users to collect data. Also the various online platforms, website helps to collect the current information and complete this study.

VII. METHODOLOGY

The descriptive survey method is used for proposed research investigation. 250 students are randomly selected and observed by researcher. Also find out there information seeking behavior while they are in accessing Information. The web based questionnaire circulated for data collection. 15% of student selected from overall population.

VIII. OER AVAILABLE AT COEP TECH UNIVERSITY

The increase in price of textbook, e- resources or reading material made a huge impact on student reading habituate. Many students could not able to purchase the desired textbook up to end of the semester, hence use of information technology and online resources increased day by day. In Today's information explosion era various website, cloud based services, mobile application, social media platforms, online reading platform e- books ,e-journals, e-database opens the thousand doors for knowledge seekers.

Various online platforms, databases, websites carries lots of information student as well teachers using those platforms for their information need, Yet, until recently, much of this material was locked up behind passwords within proprietary systems. The OER promote to break

down such barriers and to encourage and enable sharing content freely.

IX. MAJOR OER IN COEP TECH UNIVERSITY FOR COE PIANS

- **COPEN-7 Lectures:** Expert advice or Series of seven lectures is available on university portal under resources basic requirement to view the lectures series Adobe Flash Player 9 or higher.
- **NPTEL Lectures Series:** DIGIMAT the video learning platform is also available on university portal DIGIMAT - The No.1 HTML-5 and QR Code based platform helps you to quickly search / filter from 36,200+ NPTEL video lectures.
- **COEP NDLI Club:** National Digital Library of India (NDLI) is a virtual repository of learning resources which is a repository with search/browse facilities & provides a host of services for the learner community. A virtual platform free for one and all. COEP NDLI Club conducts a various webinar, special talks, and guest lecturers for students. The 2051 club members participated in club events and 43 online events conducted successfully by COEP NDLI Club.
- **COEP wiki:** A Wiki is a web site developed collaboratively by a community of users, allowing any user to add and edit content. This Wiki is set up to help carry out assignments for students of College of Engineering Pune . Student can create pages, discuss assignments on these pages, upload images (currently only in specific formats), etc.

Fig. 2: COEP Moodle

- **Moodle is a Learning Platform or course management system (CMS)** – COEP procured the Cisco Webex licenses for online teaching the training sessions were scheduled on the use of MOODLE and shared recorded videos on the ease of use of MOODLE
- **Virtual labs:** COEP participated in v-Lab project a project by ministry of education government of India under national mission on education to provide a complete Learning Management System around the Virtual Labs where the students/ teachers can avail the various tools for

learning, including additional web-resources, video-lectures, animated demonstrations and self-evaluation.

Broad area of virtual labs:

- Electronic and telecommunication
- Computer science & Engineering
- Electrical Engineering
- Mechanical Engineering
- Civil Engineering & Others .

X. OTHER OPEN EDUCATIONAL RESOURCES

There are large number of open educational resources available worldwide and also available for COEPians as per the all India council for technical education (AICTE) letter No-F. No./FDC/DIR (PS)/MISC./01 /2022-23 Dated:- 03/01/2023 COEP Tech University provide following OER for users :

- **Rice University Open Stax:** This OER is a part of Rice University with the mission to improve educational access and learning for everyone. URL: (<https://openstax.org/>)
- **e-Campus Ontario:** It is a provincially-funded non-profit organization that leads a consortium of the province's publicly-funded colleges, universities and indigenous institutes to develop and test online learning tools to advance the use of education technology and digital learning environments. URL: (<https://www.ecampusontario.ca/>)
- **Skills Commons:** This OER is to accelerate the democratization of education for all through open educational services and resources enabling individuals, communities, educational institutions, organizations, and businesses to prepare people for successful employment in the 21st Century. URL: (<https://www.skillscommons.org/>)

- **Libre Texts:** The objective of this platform is to unite students, faculty and scholars in a cooperative effort to develop an easy-to-use online platform for the construction, customization, and dissemination of open educational resources (OER) to reduce the burdens of unreasonable textbook costs to our students and society. URL: (<https://libretexts.org/>)
- **Saylor Academy:** It offers free and open online courses to all who want to learn. There are nearly 100 full-length courses at the college and professional levels, each built by subject matter experts. All courses are available to complete at your pace, on your schedule, and free of cost. URL: (<https://www.saylor.org/>)
- **Commonwealth of Learning (COL):** Online micro courses platform for different courses. (URL: <https://colcolynnons.or12/>)
- **British Columbia Open Text Book Project:** The 13 C Open Collections by B Campus is a curated selection of open educational resources (OER) that can be accessed by educators in B.C. and beyond to use in the classroom, in an institutional learning management system, or on other teaching and learning platforms. URL: (<https://collection.bccampus.ca/>)

XI. NIELSON USABILITY MODEL (1993)

Fig. 3: Nielson Usability model

Neilson first identify he attributes of usability which are efficiency, Learnability, satisfaction, Memorability etc. researcher used this model to investigate OER available at COEP Tech. University.

A. Research Findings

The findings of the study are presented in the following tables with explanations:

Sr No	User perception	YES (%)	NO (%)	Not sure (%)
1	I am using OER for my Information need	80	10	10
2	Do you know OER are in online format	85	10	5
3	Data in OER is valid or not	60	35	5
4	Male /Female users	M45	F55	-
5	Your Institute organize orientation program for OER	95	5	-
6	Did you get all content in OER	70	30	
7	OER are easy to use	90	10	-
8	OER is freely available open access resources	70	10	20
9	OER help to prepare notes /project/article	98	2	-
10	OER help to connect with other learner community	90	5	5

Table 1: Student Awareness Of Oer Usages: (In %)

Above table shows details opinion of users of COEP Tech University the particular question asked during data collection by questionnaire the percentage of users about awareness of OER is 92% it shows the positive result about awareness many students know what is OER and they use OER for their information need. Some student use efficiently but they don't know data in OER IS valid or not. The overall table indicates the users awareness about OER.

XII. CONCLUSION

The rising prices of almost all the things including educational and learning material it is impossible to procure all type of material for users so OER helps to reduce this financial stress over any educational institute. Also any underdevelopment institute it help to satisfied users needs also in above research researchers had discussed about the validity and legal issue of OER. in other word we can say OER help to boost information need of users. In this survey also found that the student had high level of awareness of OER it made positive impact on their education need. Here alternative hypothesis being accepted because there is clear connection between user awareness and use of OER. Also teacher and student of COEP Tech University should use OER as a additional information source. In the information explosion era it is very difficult for any stakeholder to select a valid platform to serve users need this research help to determine or to pick specific platform for any institute to facilitate their patron.

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